

1 Imprints of **Periodic** Body-Movement **Timing** onto Subsequent Processing of
2 **Auditory Musical Rhythm**

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32

Abstract

33 Music often entrains rhythmic body movement (e.g., dancing, locomotion). In turn,
34 body-movement can also shape rhythm processing. Although this phenomenon is often
35 leveraged in music learning, the behavioural and brain processes underlying
36 movement-driven perceptual plasticity remain understudied. This registered report
37 aimed at capturing these processes using electroencephalography (EEG) and hand
38 clapping to an auditory rhythm (derived from West/Central African musical traditions),
39 tested with African-enculturated participants. Neural and behavioural measures were
40 conducted separately, both before vs. after a body-movement session, which primed
41 different metrical interpretations through stepping and clapping along with the stimulus
42 (either three-beat or four-beat metre, the latter being conventionally associated with
43 this rhythm in the participants' culture). Behavioural data showed a propensity to clap
44 the primed metre to a greater extent after vs. before the movement session, indicating
45 that short-term motor engagement can shape rhythmic behaviour beyond cultural
46 experience. In contrast, EEG data did not show corresponding enhancement of neural
47 responses, suggesting that a single brief movement session may not be sufficient as a
48 short-term learning experience to stabilise a metre representation that can be
49 reactivated automatically (i.e., without an explicit, related task). Nonetheless,
50 participants were able to draw upon such short-term learning of metre–rhythm
51 associations to guide movement timing when required to produce overt movement to
52 such a rhythm. Together, these results highlight the interplay of motor engagement,
53 multisensory integration, and cultural experience in shaping rhythm perception.

54 *Keywords:* music cognition; cultural experience; rhythmic entrainment; beat and
55 meter perception; sensorimotor synchronisation; body movement; EEG; frequency
56 tagging

57 Imprints of **Periodic** Body-Movement **Timing** onto Subsequent Processing of
58 **Auditory Musical Rhythm**

59 **Foreword**

60 This study is part of a larger programmatic registered report aiming to capture
61 direct neuroscientific evidence for the shaping of auditory information by the pace of
62 previous movements with a cross-cultural perspective (Guérin et al., 2024). Specifically,
63 West/Central African- and European-enculturated individuals were tested in two
64 distinct studies, to demonstrate the culture-driven neural plasticity in rhythm
65 processing in humans. Each study was intended to test a set of specific intra-cultural
66 hypotheses, and the two data sets were also combined to examine a series of
67 cross-cultural hypotheses. The present study reports findings from the
68 African-enculturated participant group.

69 **Introduction**

70 Animals commonly rely on rhythmic movements to explore their environment,
71 which facilitates the sampling of sensory information (Gibson, 1962; Zalta et al., 2020).
72 This so-called ‘active sensing’ process is easily conceivable in the context of vision,
73 somatosensation, or olfaction, where eye, finger, or sniffing movements directly
74 contribute to sensory exploration. In the scope of audition, the way movement might
75 shape perception is less straightforward. This is especially true in species who do not
76 use echolocation as a main sensory system, such as humans, in whom the degree to
77 which such an active sensing process is used to regulate and facilitate sensory inflow –
78 thereby optimising sensitivity to external sounds – remains unclear (Schroeder et al.,
79 2010). This registered report aims to capture how the pace of body movements leaves
80 its imprint on the subsequent processing of auditory information in humans. It
81 capitalises on the intrinsic interplay between music and body movement, and related
82 processes of multisensory integration (i.e., audition, vision, and proprioception).

83 Music has accompanied human activities since the dawn of time (Brown, 2022;
84 Garfinkel, 2018; Vander Elst et al., 2023). Specifically, musical rhythm provides an
85 anchor to time movements through its often highly recurrent temporal structure, a

86 process referred to as *sensorimotor synchronisation* (Repp, 2005; Repp & Su, 2013).
87 This temporal coordination between a rhythmic movement and external auditory
88 rhythm is underpinned by anticipatory mechanisms that allow individuals to estimate
89 future acoustic onsets and apply online adjustments if necessary (Cannon, 2021;
90 van der Steen & Keller, 2013; Vuust & Witek, 2014; Vuust et al., 2022).

91 To be able to form temporal expectancies when listening to music, individuals
92 need to transform complex auditory or other sensory (e.g., visual; Su, 2016) rhythmic
93 inputs into an internal representation of musical-event timing (Cannon, 2021; Large &
94 Palmer, 2002; van der Weij et al., 2017; Vuust et al., 2018). This internal representation
95 typically takes the form of a metre, which corresponds to a nested set of felt pulsations
96 that are often periodic (Lenc et al., 2021; London, 2012; Vuust and Witek, 2014; of
97 note, in the current study, ‘metre’ is used as a comprehensive term with no explicit
98 specification about the number of pulse layers, thus minimising underlying
99 assumptions). Importantly, the metre perceived when experiencing a given rhythm is
100 not driven by the input in a one-to-one fashion. In other words, the perceptual system
101 does not simply search for an internal periodic template that provides the closest match
102 to periodicities marked by the arrangement of prominent acoustic events over time.
103 Rather, meter perception can be considered a form of perceptual categorisation (Lenc
104 et al., 2025), thus relying on a flexible mapping between a rhythmic sensory input and
105 an internal representation of periodic pulses (Iversen et al., 2009; Repp, 2010; Schaefer
106 et al., 2011). Arguably, this mapping is far from trivial, especially when the sensory
107 input lacks unambiguous periodic arrangement of salient acoustic features – as in
108 so-called syncopated (Witek, 2017) or contrametric (Kolinski, 1973) rhythms, where
109 rhythmic and metric structures show a degree of incongruency, which are typical for
110 numerous genres of popular, groove-based music around the world (e.g., jazz, funk,
111 breakbeat, Afro-Cuban, and African styles; Huron & Ommen, 2006; London et al.,
112 2017; Temperley, 1999, 2000). In these specific cases, metre perception must rely on
113 internal processes beyond mere detection of acoustic periodicities in the relevant
114 temporal range (Lenc et al., 2021; London, 2012). One of these processes is the learned

115 *association* between contextual cues (e.g., particular rhythmic figure, timbre, tempo,
116 and social setting) and a specific internal metre (Kaplan et al., 2022; London, 2012;
117 London et al., 2017; van der Weij et al., 2017).

118 Several theoretical models have been proposed to describe the nature of
119 associations between a rhythmic figure (i.e., a temporal pattern of [sounds acoustic,](#)
120 [visual or proprioceptive events](#)) and an internal metre. These models emphasise to
121 different degrees the role of active body movement in learning to map a particular
122 rhythmic stimulus onto an internal representation of a particular metre. For instance,
123 the predictive-coding theory of music claims that when listening to music, the brain
124 deploys a predictive model (based on prior experience) that guides our perception
125 (Vuust et al., 2018, 2022). Movement production would allow to form highly-precise
126 [auditory](#) predictions [of auditory event sequences](#) due to the combination of the
127 rhythmic input with multiple sensory information (e.g., proprioceptive and visual
128 inputs; Manning & Schutz, 2015; Wing et al., 2010). Another prominent [theory model,](#)
129 the neural resonance theory, proposes metre perception to emerge due to
130 synchronisation between a given rhythmic stimulus and the intrinsic dynamics of
131 endogenous oscillatory brain networks (Large & Kolen, 1994; Large & Snyder, 2009;
132 Large et al., 2023). Notably, according to this theoretical model, oscillatory interactions
133 between the auditory and motor areas of the brain would be crucial for metre
134 perception to arise (Large et al., 2015; Tichko et al., 2021).

135 Also suggesting an effect of movement-related processes on metre perception, the
136 active sensing framework states that the motor system modulates the cortical
137 processing of auditory information by refining attention surrounding relevant sensory
138 information (Morillon et al., 2014, 2015). Specifically, motor delta oscillations (0.5–4
139 Hz) would sharpen the brain processing of rhythmic sounds by synchronising the
140 temporal fluctuations of attention with the timing of auditory events (Morillon et al.,
141 2019; Zalta et al., 2020). [More radically,](#) the action simulation for auditory prediction
142 (ASAP) hypothesis proposes that the simulation of periodic movement shapes metre
143 perception (Patel & Iversen, 2014; Proksch et al., 2020). According to this hypothesis,

144 cortical motor planning regions would [thus](#) be entrained by an implicit and automatic
145 process of movement simulation triggered by rhythmic sounds, and this oscillatory
146 pattern would propagate to auditory areas, influencing the metric interpretation of
147 rhythm (Iversen et al., 2009). Although these theoretical models of musical rhythm
148 perception diverge in a number of ways (e.g., anatomical substrates, directionality of
149 relationship between movement and meter perception), they can be viewed as mutually
150 reinforcing (e.g., by describing mechanisms at the brain level or at the cognitive level;
151 see Large et al., 2023; Zalta et al., 2024); and importantly, each of them presupposes a
152 strong role of motor production in metre perception.

153 The effect of body-movement pace on the subsequent internal representation of
154 rhythm has been reported in several empirical studies using behavioural methods. For
155 example, both active and passive body movement coordinated with a rhythmic pattern
156 according to a specific metre was found to bias the way individuals subsequently
157 perceive a rhythm, possibly through vestibular-mediated processes (Phillips-Silver &
158 Trainor, 2008; Trainor et al., 2009). Specifically, both adults and infants have been
159 shown to develop increased expectancy of salient sounds at those positions within a
160 rhythmic pattern that were aligned with the metre the individual had previously moved
161 to (Phillips-Silver & Trainor, 2005, 2007; Su & Pöppel, 2012). [Nonetheless](#) [However](#), the
162 behavioural measures used in these studies only constitute an indirect way to capture
163 the internal representation of metre elicited by a rhythm (Lenc et al., 2021). Convergent
164 evidence across various forms of measurements (e.g., measurements of both the neural
165 and behavioural responses as recorded in separate sessions in response to rhythmic
166 stimuli) could thus help moving a significant step toward a comprehensive
167 understanding of how movement can shape the internal representation of metre. One
168 neuroimaging study found that the neural responses to a rhythmic pattern were
169 significantly bolstered after body-movement production, selectively at frequencies
170 related to the metre that participants had moved to (Chemin et al., 2014). However, the
171 rhythmic stimulus used in this study contained prominent metre-related periodicities in
172 its acoustic structure, thus making it hard to disentangle effects driven by an actual

173 internal representation of metre from effects related to low-level sensory processing of
174 the rhythmic input.

175 To move a critical step forward, the objective of this study was to capture direct
176 neuroscientific evidence for the shaping of auditory information by the pace of previous
177 movement. Ecological plausibility was ensured by a cultural congruence between the
178 stimulus and the participant sample. If significant, the effect of [short-term prior](#)
179 [experience of rhythmic body movements](#) would thus likely be intrinsically supported by
180 a number of distinct processes, including motor planning, visual, auditory,
181 somatosensory and vestibular cues combined together (Phillips-Silver & Trainor, 2008;
182 Trainor et al., 2009). Movement-related shaping of auditory information [processing](#) was
183 purposely adopted in the current study (a) for its ecological validity in music and dance
184 contexts, and (b) to increase the likelihood of eliciting an effect in the listening block
185 subsequent to the movement priming, due to the mixture of multisensory effects
186 expected to strengthen carry-over effects. Hence, our objective was *not* to define the
187 necessary and sufficient mechanism for the effect of movement on rhythm perception to
188 take place, but rather to capture the brain processes underlying this holistic effect,
189 while not precluding mental imagery of beat or priming by auditory inputs (as in Nave
190 et al., 2022) that could also significantly shape auditory information.

191 **Research Hypotheses**

192 This article is part of a larger programmatic registered report (Guérin et al.,
193 2024), which proposed two distinct but complementary studies to address broad
194 research questions – and thus resulted in two Stage 2 articles. Specifically, this Stage 2
195 article targeted African-enculturated individuals, while another Stage 2 focused on
196 [Western European](#)-enculturated individuals and the cross-cultural comparisons.

197 In the present study, one group of African-enculturated individuals participated
198 in a ~15-min body-movement session consisting of stepping and clapping to a rhythm in
199 synchrony with an overlaid drum sound indicating a three-beat metrical interpretation
200 of the rhythm. Another group of African-enculturated individuals engaged in the same
201 protocol but following a four-beat metrical interpretation of the same rhythm. The

202 rhythmic input consisted ~~in~~ of a context-free version ~~derived from~~ of a rhythmic pattern
203 spanning 12 elements often used in musical traditions from West to Central Africa
204 (Agawu, 2006; Kubik, 2010; Poole, 2018), and ~~frequently variously~~ referred to as
205 Bembé, ~~bell/elave pattern~~, or standard ~~timeline bell pattern~~. Specifically, this rhythmic
206 ~~pattern often~~ serves ~~a key role at indicating the~~ as a temporal reference in African (and
207 African-derived) music (Agawu, 2006; Kubik, 2010; Locke, 1982; Polak, 2026; Poole,
208 2018; Toussaint, 2003). While empirical evidence is still lacking, ethnomusicological
209 work suggests that widespread metric mode among populations enculturated in West
210 and Central African musical environments is to experience 12-element rhythmic
211 patterns as suggesting a four-beat metre (Agawu, 2006; Locke, 1982; Poole, 2018). This
212 mode is relatively less prominent in populations enculturated with Euro-American
213 popular or art music traditions. By contrast, individuals with such backgrounds often
214 carry metric modes that would map the same 12-element rhythms to a three-beat metre
215 (Blacking, 1967).

216 The neural activity of participants was recorded using EEG while they stayed
217 still and listened to the same rhythmic input in two sessions directly preceding and
218 following the body-movement session. At the end of each EEG session, participants
219 were asked to clap along with the rhythm as an ecological index of behavioural
220 entrainment to the perceived metre (for a discussion on the importance of using
221 ecological behaviours in timing research, see Rose et al., 2021). A frequency-tagging
222 approach was used to measure the relative prominence of the periodicity corresponding
223 to the perceived metre in the signal of interest (i.e., acoustic input, EEG response
224 elicited by the acoustic input, clapping movement to the acoustic input; Lenc et al.,
225 2021, 2022). Over the past 10 years, this approach has proven to be useful in objectively
226 measuring the input–output transformation performed by the brain, and how this
227 transformation might relate to metre perception (Lenc et al., 2022; Nave et al., 2022;
228 Nozaradan et al., 2017; Stupacher et al., 2016). Here, we predicted that an enhanced
229 representation of the metre will be observed in the post-movement neural and
230 behavioural responses to the rhythmic input (see Table 1). This enhancement was

231 expected to be selective to the metre conveyed by prior movement and magnified for the
232 metre predominant in the participant's culture.

233 We hypothesised that the amplitude of neural responses at metre frequencies
234 (i.e., three-beat frequencies in the three-beat condition, and four-beat frequencies in the
235 four-beat condition; see Methods) will be enhanced after vs. before the movement
236 session (H_{1a}). This session effect (pre- vs. post-movement) would confirm that
237 short-term multimodal ~~exposure to~~ *experience of* a specific metre as induced by active,
238 intentional movement shapes subsequent internal representation of an auditory rhythm,
239 possibly through perceptual learning (Cannon, 2021; Pearce, 2018). As an alternative,
240 an absence of effect would indicate that (a) the metrical interpretation was already
241 strongly associated with this rhythmic pattern before the body-movement session,
242 possibly driven by a mix of biological and cultural factors (see Kaplan et al., 2022;
243 van der Weij et al., 2017); or (b) the movement session did not provide a sufficient
244 combination of cues (e.g., auditory, vestibular, tactile) to subsequently stabilise a
245 metrical interpretation in such a short period of time.

246 In addition, we hypothesised this session effect on neural responses to be
247 magnified in the four-beat condition (H_{1b}). This interaction effect would indicate that
248 moving to the rhythm is more effective at shaping subsequent neural representation of
249 an auditory rhythm when executed according to a culturally relevant metre (i.e.,
250 four-beat metre). On the other hand, if the session effect is greater in the three-beat
251 condition, this would suggest that, in the culturally familiar condition, the skill level is
252 already relatively high, resulting in a ceiling effect.

253 We also hypothesised that similar effects will be observed at the behavioural
254 level, namely that the amplitude of metre frequencies will be selectively enhanced in the
255 clapping trials (H_{2a}), and that the four-beat movement condition will yield the most
256 powerful effect (H_{2b}). Consistency between brain and behavioural effects would indicate
257 that the observed improvement at clapping the metre in the post-movement session
258 (assumed to be closely related to the way individuals 'feel' the metre, due to explicit
259 instructions) is associated with an increased selective representation of the metre

260 frequencies in neural activity. Conversely, observing a significant effect of [the movement](#)
261 session in neural but not behavioural responses would suggest that participants may not
262 necessarily [be able to](#) use the internal representation of the metre induced by the
263 movement session to guide overt movement beyond the movement session itself.

264 **Methods**

265 **Ethical Clearance**

266 The ethics committee of the Université Catholique de Louvain, Belgium,
267 approved the present study (ref. 2018-353). Informed consent were obtained from all the
268 participants prior to inclusion in the study. Participants were compensated for their
269 time.

270 **Participants**

271 Adult volunteers considered eligible to participate in the study were aged
272 between 18 and 45 years, non-musicians and non-dancers, free of sensory (i.e., no
273 auditory impairment or uncorrected visual impairment) and motor dysfunctions (i.e., no
274 upper- and/or lower-limb disorders), and not self-identify as having psychiatric or
275 neurological disorders. In the present study, non-musicians or non-dancers were defined
276 as those meeting at least two out of the three following criteria: (a) not considering
277 themselves as such, (b) not having more than four years of practice, and (c) not having
278 played an instrument/danced in a concert or performance on stage in front of an
279 audience.

280 Participants were included in the African-enculturated group if they
281 self-reported that (a) themselves or both their parents have lived, at least for the first
282 15 years of their lives, in one of the following countries: Mali, Côte d'Ivoire, Togo,
283 Benin, Cameroon, Gabon, Republic of Congo, or Democratic Republic of Congo; and
284 (b) they speak fluently and at least 1h/week one of the idioms (i.e., languages, dialects)
285 from the above-mentioned countries. The screening questionnaire is available for
286 consultation in Supplementary File 1.

287 The sample size for the critical statistical test of each research hypothesis was
288 calculated using R with the 'pwr' and 'WebPower' packages (code is available here:

289 <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10221480>). The EEG and behavioural results of
290 Chemin et al. (2014) were used as a parameter for H_1-H_2 , with one-tailed tests. For H_1 ,
291 the power analysis indicated that eight participants would be required for the session
292 effect ($d = 1.53$; $\alpha = .02$; $1-\beta = .90$) and 20 participants per movement condition would
293 be necessary for the interaction effect between movement condition and session ($f =$
294 0.89 ; $\alpha = .02$; $1-\beta = .90$). For H_2 , six participants would be required for the session
295 effect ($d = 1.77$; $\alpha = .02$; $1-\beta = .90$) and 20 participants per movement condition would
296 be necessary for the interaction effect between movement condition and session ($f =$
297 0.89 ; $\alpha = .02$; $1-\beta = .90$). Therefore, a total sample of 40 participants (i.e., 20 per
298 movement condition) was recruited for the present study.

299 The small telescopes approach was used to determine the smallest effect size of
300 interest (SESOI; i.e., the difference that is considered large enough to be meaningful;
301 Simonsohn, 2015). Accordingly, the SESOI was set to the effect size that an earlier study
302 would have had 33% power to detect (Lakens et al., 2018). Here again, the behavioural
303 and EEG results of Chemin et al. (2014) were used as parameters for H_1-H_2 , with
304 one-tailed tests. The SESOI computations were performed using R (code is available as
305 supplementary material here: <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10221480>) and
306 the outputs are displayed in Table 1.

307 **Experimental Procedure and Tasks**

308 *Experimental Procedure*

309 Each participant was administered three sessions (~20 min each) on the same
310 day. In the pre- and post-movement sessions, the participant was asked to perform a
311 separate listening and hand-clapping task in a fixed order (see Figure 1, Panel A). Brain
312 activity of the participant was recorded with EEG during the listening task, and
313 behavioural data was collected during the hand-clapping task. In the movement session,
314 half of the participants engaged in the three-beat movement condition while the other
315 half participated in the four-beat movement condition (i.e., between-subjects study
316 design with repeated measures). EEG data was not collected during the movement
317 session. To verify effective behavioural synchronisation in the movement session, an

318 accelerometer was attached to the right foot of the participant and hand-clapping
319 sounds were collected through a microphone. To control for the absence of body
320 movement during the pre- and post-movement sessions, the accelerometer was placed on
321 the participant's head.

322 In the pre- and post-movement sessions, the participant was seated in a
323 comfortable chair, with their head resting against the back of the chair. In these
324 sessions, the participant was instructed to relax, avoid any unnecessary movement, and
325 keep their eyes fixated on a marker displayed on the wall ~1 m in front of them (to
326 minimise large eye movements). During the movement session, the EEG electrode cables
327 were unplugged from the amplifier and attached on the participant's shoulders to free
328 their movements.

329 *Auditory Stimulus*

330 **Description.** The rhythmic pattern used throughout the experiment originates
331 from West and Central Africa, where it often functions as a timeline pattern. It is often
332 referred to variously addressed as Bembé, bell/clave pattern, or standard timeline bell
333 (Locke, 1982; Toussaint, 2003), among other denominations. In this experiment, this
334 pattern had a duration of 2.4 s and was seamlessly repeated 17 times to form a long
335 sequence, with a total duration of 40.8 s (see Figure 1). Its 'x.x.xx.x.x.x' structure is
336 based on a 12-interval grid ($200 \text{ ms} \times 12 = 2.4 \text{ s}$), following a specific arrangement of
337 seven 200-ms sound events (depicted by the 'x', and made of a 200-Hz pure tones with
338 10-ms rise and 50-ms fall linear ramps) and five 200-ms silent intervals (depicted by the
339 ':').

340 This rhythmic stimulus is particularly relevant to the present study for several
341 reasons. Firstly, the rhythmic pattern is culturally valid due to its wide use across
342 musical traditions in Central and West Africa (Locke, 1982; Temperley, 2000). Yet, the
343 pattern can be presented in a decontextualized fashion for the purposes of the current
344 study (e.g., by using pure tones instead of a clave sound that typically delivers the
345 pattern in stylistically valid contexts), thus minimising the interference caused by
346 non-rhythmic contextual cues in participants familiar with musical repertoires

347 containing this pattern. Unlike stimuli used in the majority of prior studies (e.g.,
348 Chemin et al., 2014; Phillips-Silver & Trainor, 2005, 2007), the groups of tones making
349 up the pattern are arranged in a way that a tone does not systematically coincide with
350 each beat, thus reducing the likelihood of acoustic or low-level sensory confounds (see
351 Lenc et al., 2021; Nozaradan et al., 2016). This holds for beat pulses that are used in
352 both the three- or four-beat metre condition. Moreover, an overlap between the internal
353 beat and the arrangement of tones in the rhythm cannot be achieved by simply shifting
354 the phase (or alignment) of the beat with respect to the stimulus.

355 In the movement session, a metronome-like acoustic pulse was added to the
356 auditory stimulus and served as a cue to the beat from the targeted metre. This pulse
357 consisted of a low-pitched drum sound presented isochronously with an inter-onset
358 interval of 800 ms in the three-beat metre condition and 600 ms in the four-beat metre
359 condition, thus yielding three or four drum cues per repetition of the 2.4-s rhythmic
360 pattern, respectively. In the three-beat metre condition, the pulses were aligned with
361 the first, fifth, and ninth time point on the grid used to generate the rhythmic pattern.
362 In the four-beat metre condition, the pulses occurred at the first, fourth, seventh, and
363 tenth grid point (see Figure 2, Panel B). The drum sound coinciding with the first grid
364 point was accented (sound intensity increased by 2.5 dB) to emphasise the onset of each
365 repetition of the pattern. Three additional repetitions of the rhythmic pattern without
366 the overlaid pulse were appended at the end of the auditory stimulus (40.8 s of auditory
367 stimulation with the overlaid pulse and 7.2 without, for a total trial duration of 48 s; see
368 Figure 1, Panel A). The three auditory stimuli were generated using MATLAB (version
369 R2022a; MathWorks, Portola Valley, CA).

370 **Sound Analysis.** To control for acoustic or low-level sensory confounds that
371 may bias the results, it is critical to measure how prominent the periodicities
372 corresponding to the three- and four-beat metrical interpretations are in the rhythmic
373 stimulus (Lenc et al., 2021). To this end, the amplitude envelope of the 40.8-s auditory
374 sequence was extracted using a Hilbert transform and converted into the frequency
375 domain using a fast Fourier transform (Lenc et al., 2021; Nozaradan et al., 2017),

376 allowing to estimate the prominence of periodicities in the continuous modulation of the
377 stimulus acoustic features. The obtained envelope spectrum contains 12 distinct
378 amplitude peaks (see Figure 2, Panel A), corresponding to the repetition frequency of
379 the whole rhythmic pattern (i.e., $1/2.4 \text{ s} = 0.42 \text{ Hz}$) and its harmonics up to the
380 shortest intervals between single events (i.e., $1/0.2 \text{ s} = 5 \text{ Hz}$; Lenc et al., 2021). To
381 match analysis of the EEG signals (see below ‘EEG Data’ subsection), the first and last
382 frequency (i.e., 0.42 and 5 Hz, respectively) of the spectrum were discarded from further
383 computation.

384 To assess the relative prominence of frequencies considered as related to the
385 metre vs. the other, metre-unrelated frequencies, the magnitudes of responses at the 10
386 frequencies of interest were then converted into z scores following Equation 1 (see
387 Figure 2, Panel B; Lenc et al., 2018):

$$z_i = \frac{A_i - \bar{A}_{\text{all}}}{s_{\text{all}}} \quad (1)$$

388 where i is a given frequency of interest, A is the amplitude, and s is the standard
389 deviation. Finally, the obtained z scores were averaged across metre frequencies (i.e.,
390 the frequency corresponding to the metre periodicity and harmonics: 1.25 and 3.75 Hz
391 in the three-beat condition, and 0.83, 1.67, 3.33 and 4.17 Hz in the four-beat condition).
392 Note that the sixth frequency (i.e., 2.5 Hz) was dismissed as it is found in both metrical
393 interpretations. As displayed in Figure 2 (Panel C), the stimulus contains a virtually
394 equivalent low acoustic energy (z scores < 0) at either of the two metre periodicities
395 considered here, when compared to the remaining frequencies constituting the envelope
396 spectrum of the rhythm.

397 ***Tasks Description***

398 The auditory stimuli were presented binaurally via insert earphones (ER-2,
399 Etymotic Research; air-conducted sound from the level of the participant’s clavicle to
400 decrease magnetic interferences), connected to a Fireface UC audio interface (RME
401 Audio, Haimhausen, Germany; sampling frequency = 44100 Hz; sound volume = 73 dB
402 sound pressure level [SPL]). In the listening task (i.e., during which EEG signals were
403 collected), the auditory stimulus was played to the participant while they were required

404 to perform an orthogonal task to encourage attentive listening. More precisely, the
405 participant was instructed to detect speed reduction in the temporal structure of the
406 auditory stimulus and report their response at the end of each trial (i.e., to avoid
407 speech-related artifacts during the EEG recording). This tempo change was applied to
408 the tenth repetition of the rhythmic pattern within the trial by increasing the spacing of
409 the underlying time grid by 7.5%, lengthening the duration of that repetition from 2.4 s
410 to 2.58 s. There was a total of two trials per session containing this deviant period (with
411 those trials being randomly positioned across participants), and these trials were
412 discarded from further analyses. In the hand-clapping task (i.e., which directly followed
413 the listening task in both the pre- and post-movement sessions; see Figure 1, [Panel A](#)),
414 the participant was instructed to clap along with the beat they perceived in the auditory
415 stimulus ('Clap your hands as you would clap in sync with the music at a concert').

416 During the movement session (i.e., without EEG recordings), the participant was
417 asked to step on-the-spot and clap with their hands (i.e., whole-body movements) in
418 synchrony with the beat according to a specific metrical interpretation of the rhythmic
419 pattern, as indicated with the drum cue. In the last three repetitions of the rhythmic
420 pattern, the pulse prompter was stopped, and the participant thus needed to continue
421 synchronising to the same metrical interpretation without the pulse prompter (i.e.,
422 synchronisation-continuation task; see e.g., Repp, 2001; Rose et al., 2021). Detailed
423 task instructions can be found in Supplementary File 1.

424 *Experimental Design*

425 The experiment used a fixed block-design procedure (see Figure 1), with each
426 trial lasting 40.8 s in the pre- and post-movement sessions and 48 s in the movement
427 session. The pre- and post-movement sessions were composed of 18 trials for the
428 listening task (including two randomly placed trials containing the deviant period to be
429 detected for the orthogonal task), followed by five trials for the hand-clapping task. The
430 movement session consisted of 18 trials. To assess the participant's familiarity with the
431 stimulus, they were asked whether they recognised the rhythmic pattern during the

432 debriefing session at the end of the experiment. The total duration of the experimental
433 procedure was ~1 hr.

434 **Data Acquisition and Pre-Processing Analyses**

435 Data acquisition was performed using an ActiveTwo system (BioSemi,
436 Amsterdam, Netherlands) and facilitated by the ActiView software (version 8.13). All
437 the pre-processing analyses were performed using MATLAB (version R2022a). Data
438 collection and analysis were not performed blind to the conditions of the study. To
439 avoid a confounding effect of the experimenter, the first and second authors of this
440 article (who each led one of the two Stage 2 articles) each collected data from half of
441 the participants in the two experimental groups. Pilot tests were run ($n = 1$ in the
442 three- and four-beat movement condition) to confirm that the experimental protocol
443 and data collection were logistically feasible and that planned analyses allowed us to
444 test the research hypotheses (see Supplementary File 2).

445 **EEG Data**

446 The EEG data were recorded with 64 Ag/AgCl pin-type active electrodes placed
447 on the participant's scalp according to the International 10–20 system guidelines for
448 standard electrode placement (Jasper, 1958). In addition, two flat-type active electrodes
449 were located over the left and right mastoids. Signals were referenced to the
450 common-mode sense electrode and digitised at a 1024-Hz sampling rate. Electrodes
451 offset relative to the common mode sense (CMS) and driven leg (DRL) electrode loop
452 was kept below ± 50 mV.

453 The EEG data were pre-processed using Letswave6 built-in functions
454 (<https://github.com/NOCIONS/letswave6>) and custom MATLAB scripts. The raw
455 data were band-pass filtered using a 0.1–64 Hz Butterworth filter (4th order) in order to
456 eliminate very slow drifts and high frequencies irrelevant to the present study (while
457 also allowing further down sampling of the data if necessary). The filtered signals were
458 segmented from -5 s to +45.8 s (i.e., 5-s buffer at the beginning and end) with respect
459 to the onset to each trial. Based on visual inspection, channels containing excessive
460 artefacts or noise were linearly interpolated using the three closest channels (based on

461 Cartesian coordinates). Note that a channel that was interpolated in one EEG session
462 was also interpolated in the other EEG session of the same participant to prevent
463 confounds. 2.5% of the channels were interpolated on this basis. In addition, trials
464 showing excessive artefacts were rejected. Across all participants, seven trials were
465 rejected on this basis. The full data set of a participant were removed prior to further
466 analyses if $> 15\%$ of the channels were interpolated and/or > 3 trials per session were
467 rejected (see Figure 3). Nine participants were removed on this basis. Any excluded
468 participant were replaced to ensure that $n = 20$ per group.

469 Independent component analysis was applied to concatenated segments (from 0
470 to 40.8 s relative to the trial onset) of all trials and sessions, down-sampled to 256 Hz
471 with the purpose of reducing computation time. For each participant, the independent
472 components related to eye blinks were identified through visual inspection of the first 10
473 independent components' waveform and topography, and removed from the EEG
474 signals. Data were then re-referenced to the mean of the two mastoids electrodes,
475 averaged across trials, and epoched from 2.4 to 40.8 s with respect to trial onset (i.e.,
476 removal of the 5-s buffer and first pattern repetition), resulting in epochs of 38.4 s.

477 For each electrode, the averaged waveforms were transformed into the frequency
478 domain using fast Fourier transform, yielding a spectrum of signal amplitudes (in μV)
479 ranging from 0 to 512 Hz, with a frequency resolution of 0.026 Hz (i.e., $1/38.4$ s). To
480 obtain valid estimates of the EEG responses, the contribution of residual background
481 noise was minimised by subtracting, at each frequency bin, the mean amplitude of the
482 four neighbouring bins (2nd to 5th on both sides; see Bouvet et al., 2020; Lenc et al.,
483 2022). The frequencies were then averaged across a cluster of nine fronto-central
484 electrodes (i.e., F1, Fz, F2, FC1, FCz, FC2, C1, Cz, C2), which have been found to
485 exhibit strong frequency-tagged responses to rhythmic stimuli in previous studies (see
486 Nozaradan et al., 2012, 2016, 2017).

487 For each participant and session, the amplitude was measured at frequencies of
488 interest that were defined based on the temporal structure of the rhythmic pattern.
489 Specifically, these frequencies of interest corresponded to the pattern repetition rate and

490 harmonics ($1/2.4 \text{ s} = 0.42 \text{ Hz}$), up to the frequency equivalent to the shortest interval
491 between the onset of individual sounds composing the rhythmic pattern ($1/0.2 \text{ s} = 5$
492 Hz). This frequency range of interest was determined based on previous studies (see
493 e.g., Lenc et al., 2020, 2022), showing that surface EEG responses to rhythmic acoustic
494 patterns – similar to the one that was used in the present study – mainly project onto
495 this frequency range. From the resulting set of 12 harmonic frequencies, the first
496 frequency (i.e., 0.42 Hz) was discarded prior to further analyses, because located in a
497 frequency range that is typically strongly affected by the characteristic $1/f$ background
498 noise observed in EEG spectra (i.e., prone to unreliable measurement; Cirelli et al.,
499 2016; Lenc et al., 2022). The last harmonic frequency (i.e., 5 Hz) was also dismissed, as
500 its amplitude is likely driven by the shape of the individual 200-ms sounds composing
501 the rhythmic pattern (see Figure 2, left part, for depiction of these frequencies as
502 identified in the modulation spectrum of the stimulus).

503 From this set, the purpose of the study was to assess the relative prominence of
504 frequencies considered as related to the metre periodicity vs. the other, metre-unrelated
505 frequencies (Lenc et al., 2018). To this aim, the amplitude at each of these 10
506 frequencies of interest were converted into z scores (see Equation 1). Finally, the
507 obtained z scores were averaged across metre frequencies (i.e., 1.25 and 3.75 Hz in the
508 three-beat condition [i.e., $\bar{z}_{\text{EEG},3\text{-beat}}$], and 0.83, 1.67, 3.33, and 4.17 Hz in the four-beat
509 condition [i.e., $\bar{z}_{\text{EEG},4\text{-beat}}$]). Along the lines of the sound analysis, the sixth frequency
510 (i.e., 2.5 Hz) was dismissed as it is found in both metrical interpretations.

511 *Behavioural Data*

512 **Hand Clapping.** Hand clapping was collected using a microphone (ATR20;
513 Audio-Technica, Machida, Japan) and digitised through the Fireface UC audio interface
514 (sampling rate = 44100 Hz).

515 ***Pre- and Post-Movement Sessions.*** The continuous sound signal recorded
516 during the pre- and post-movement sessions was segmented into epochs lasting 38.4 s
517 (from 2.4 to 40.8 s with respect to trial onset). Note that the first pattern repetition of

518 each epoch was removed to match epoching of the EEG data. Claps were detected in
519 the sound signal using the ‘findpeaks’ function and IRIs were computed for each trial.

520 The recorded clapping signal was also analysed in the frequency domain,
521 similarly to the EEG and sound signals. The continuous sound signal was averaged
522 across trials. The amplitude envelope of this mean signal was extracted using a Hilbert
523 transform and transformed in the frequency domain using a fast Fourier transform
524 (frequency resolution = 0.026 Hz; i.e., 1/38.4 s trial duration). To match with the
525 analysis procedure applied on EEG data, noise subtraction was also applied to the
526 obtained spectra. Finally, $\bar{z}_{\text{clapping}}$ was computed following the same method described
527 for the EEG data (see Equation 1).

528 ***Movement Session.*** The continuous audio signal of clapping obtained from
529 participants instructed to synchronise clapping to the drum cue was segmented into
530 epochs lasting 45.6 s (from 2.4 to 48 s with respect to trial onset). Claps were detected
531 using a find peaks function applied onto the envelope extracted from the recording
532 signals. The signed asynchrony was computed as the difference between each clap and
533 its associated pulse. Signed asynchrony is negative when the clap is preceding the
534 targeted drum cue, and positive when the clap is following the targeted drum cue. The
535 mean signed asynchrony within a trial was calculated as a measure of synchrony with
536 the pulse prompter.

537 ***Stepping.*** Stepping performed during the movement session was recorded using
538 an accelerometer placed on the participant’s right foot (ADXL335; Adafruit, New York,
539 USA), and digitised through the BioSemi analog input box (sampling rate = 1024 Hz).
540 As for the hand-clapping data, the obtained continuous acceleration signal was
541 segmented into epochs lasting 45.6 s (from 2.4 to 48 s with respect to trial onset), steps
542 were detected using a find peaks function (the detected peaks corresponded to the
543 initial-contact phase; Buckley et al., 2019; Sant’Anna & Wickström, 2010), and
544 inter-response intervals (IRIs) were computed. The IRIs time series were then divided
545 by two, to account for data recorded from one foot only. The asynchrony indices were
546 computed following the same method described for the hand-clapping data.

547 *Control Measures*

548 **Effectiveness of Auditory Stimulation.** A prerequisite to our hypotheses
 549 was the ability to capture the neural responses to an auditory rhythm with EEG. As a
 550 control measure for this assumption, the frequencies of interest as determined above
 551 (i.e., 0.83, 1.25, 1.67, 2.08, 2.5, 2.92, 3.33, 3.75, and 4.17 Hz) should significantly stand
 552 out relatively to background noise in the EEG signal (see Lenc et al., 2018; Nozaradan,
 553 2014; Nozaradan et al., 2018). Thus, as a positive control, an index of standardised
 554 signal-to-noise ratio ($z_{\text{SNR,EEG}}$) of the frequencies of interest was computed from the
 555 raw, non-subtracted amplitude spectrum of EEG data averaged across the
 556 fronto-central channels (see Figure 3; Bottari et al., 2020; Vettori et al., 2020).

557 In each participant’s spectrum (without noise subtraction), the amplitude at
 558 each frequency of interest along with its 20 neighbouring bins (10 on both sides,
 559 representative of local background noise) was selected, thus resulting in 10 segments of
 560 21 values. These segments were then averaged, yielding an averaged segment where the
 561 11th value thus corresponded to the averaged amplitude across the 10 frequencies of
 562 interest. This averaged segment was then standardised into a z score with Equation 2:

$$z_{\text{SNR,EEG}} = \frac{A_{11\text{th}} - \bar{A}_{\text{background}}}{s_{\text{background}}} \quad (2)$$

563 where A is the amplitude and s is the standard deviation. This index served as a
 564 measure of the overall prominence of EEG responses to the auditory stimulus over
 565 background noise.

566 **Absence of Rhythmic Head Movements During EEG Recordings.** A
 567 possible confounding factor of the present study was that the selective enhancement of
 568 EEG responses at metre-related frequencies was not due to neural responses per se but
 569 to unintentional rhythmic movements of the participant’s head while they listened to
 570 the rhythmic stimulus. To control for this potential artefact, head movements were
 571 recorded using the accelerometer during the listening trials of the pre- and post-training
 572 sessions. The $z_{\text{SNR,head}}$ of metre-related frequencies (i.e., 1.25, 2.50, and 3.75 Hz) was
 573 computed following the same method described for the EEG data (see Equation 2). This
 574 index served as an indicator of head synchronisation with metre-related frequencies.

575 **Statistical Analyses**576 ***Data Eligible for Analysis***

577 **Outcome-Neutral Criteria.** As described in more details above, only data
578 coming from participants with $\leq 15\%$ of interpolated channels and ≤ 3 rejected trials
579 per session were analysed (see Figure 3).

580 **Positive Control.** No participant's data set was excluded from the analyses
581 because $z_{\text{SNR,EEG}} < 1.96$ (i.e., $\alpha > .02$), indicating that neural responses were elicited by
582 the rhythmic stimulus in every participant.

583 ***Performed Analyses***

584 R was used for the statistical analyses, with alpha set at $p < .020$ (i.e., in accord
585 with the strictest available stipulations from the list of *PCI RR*-friendly journals). For
586 each statistical comparison, the effect sizes (i.e., η_p^2 , Cohen's d) are reported as a
587 quantification of the experimental-effect magnitude and interpreted in accord with
588 Cohen's (1988) guidelines. For effect sizes that are presented as Cohen's d , $d < 0.5$ was
589 considered as small, $d \geq 0.5$ as medium, and $d \geq 0.8$ as large. Where effect sizes are
590 presented as η_p^2 , $\eta_p^2 \geq .01$ was considered as small, $\eta_p^2 \geq .06$ as medium, and $\eta_p^2 \geq .14$ as
591 large. To test the robustness of our statistical outcomes (for the importance of
592 conducting multiverse analyses, see Wagenmakers et al., 2023), linear mixed models
593 were also used to test each hypothesis (with the 'lme4' and 'emmeans' packages), and
594 the results are reported in Supplementary File 3.

595 To examine H_1-H_2 , a two-way mixed-model analysis of variance (ANOVA;
596 Session [pre vs. post movement] \times Movement Condition [three- vs. four-beat metre])
597 was applied on the two dependent variables, \bar{z}_{EEG} and $\bar{z}_{\text{clapping}}$ (see Table 1). To
598 demonstrate that periodic head movements did not contribute significantly to the
599 effects found in the EEG (if any), an identical ANOVA model was applied on $z_{\text{SNR,head}}$.

600 Normality of residuals was checked using the R 'performance' package (Lüdtke
601 et al., 2021); if violated, the data were normalised using a transformation that will be
602 contingent on data distribution curves (e.g., ~~log10~~, ~~cube root~~). Where Mauchly's tests
603 indicated violations of the sphericity assumption, Greenhouse–Geisser corrections were

604 applied. Independent and pairwise post hoc t tests with Bonferroni adjustments for
605 multiple comparisons were used where necessary to identify where differences lie.

606

Results

607 Demographic information about our sample along with data about familiarity
608 with the rhythmic pattern are available in Figure 4 (Panel A and Panel B, respectively).

609 Data Screening and Diagnostics

610 Data screening indicated that there were two univariate outliers, associated with
611 \bar{z}_{EEG} ($k = 1$), and $z_{\text{SNR,head}}$ ($k = 1$) measures. These were adjusted using a winsorization
612 procedure (Sullivan et al., 2021) until they came within the range $-3.29 < z < +3.29$ (see
613 Tabachnick & Fidell, 2018). Normality tests indicated that $z_{\text{SNR,head}}$ exhibited instances
614 of non-normality ($p < .001$). A square root transformation was applied to remedy this.

615 EEG Data

616 The RM ANOVA showed no significant main effect of session, $F(1, 38) < 0.01$, p
617 $= .969$, $\eta_p^2 < .01$, or movement condition, $F(1, 38) = 0.25$, $p = .617$, $\eta_p^2 < .01$ (see
618 Figure 5). The Session \times Movement Condition interaction was also nonsignificant, $F(1,$
619 $38) = 0.36$, $p = .554$, $\eta_p^2 < .01$. Overall, the results indicated that amplitude of neural
620 responses at metre frequencies primed during the preceding body-movement session
621 were not enhanced after vs. before the movement session.

622 The original selection of metre-related and metre-unrelated frequencies was
623 determined from both the stimulus spectrum and plausible beat periodicities
624 compatible with each metrical interpretation. As a robustness check, an alternative
625 selection of metre-related frequencies solely based on the rate of the learning cue during
626 the body-movement session was also considered. These additional analyses are reported
627 in Supplementary File 4. The neural results remained unchanged.

628 Additionally, due to the disparity in the number of metre-related frequencies
629 between the two metrical interpretations, the value of \bar{z} is constrained to a range of -1.16
630 to $+1.16$ in the four-beat metre condition, whereas in the three-beat metre condition, it
631 can vary between -1.90 and $+1.90$. Additional analyses to address this compression
632 effect, both for the registered analyses and the selection of metre-related frequencies

633 based on the learning cues (see Supplementary File 4), are detailed in Supplementary
634 File 5. However, the results remained unchanged after controlling for this effect.

635 **Behavioural Data**

636 *Pre- and Post-Movement Sessions*

637 The RM ANOVA showed a significant main effect of session, $F(1, 38) = 13.43$, p
638 $< .001$, $\eta_p^2 = .26$, with larger $\bar{z}_{\text{clapping}}$ after ($M = 0.49$, $SD = 0.67$) when compared to
639 before the movement ($M = 0.13$, $SD = 0.71$, $d = 0.58$; see Figure XX). Note that the
640 effect size is larger than the required SESOI (see Table 1), which indicated that the
641 effect is sufficiently strong to be considered meaningful. The main effect of movement
642 condition was nonsignificant, $F(1, 38) = 0.57$, $p = .455$, $\eta_p^2 = .01$. The Session \times
643 Movement Condition interaction was also nonsignificant, $F(1, 38) = 0.45$, $p = .505$, η_p^2
644 $= .01$. Overall, the results indicated that the participants clapped periodically following
645 the metre as primed in the preceding body-movement session to a greater extent after
646 vs. before the movement session.

647 With the alternative selection of metre-related frequencies reflecting the rate of
648 the learning cue (see Supplementary File 4), the main effect of session was no longer
649 significant with the stringent p value adopted in the study ($.050 > p > .020$). However,
650 a main effect of condition emerged, corroborating the hypothesis of a stronger
651 interpretation of the rhythm according to its associated cultural convention (i.e., higher
652 z scores in the four-beat condition).

653 Additional analyses to address the above-mentioned compression effect are
654 detailed in Supplementary File 4. Overall, these analyses corroborated the results, but
655 also showed an additional main effect of condition in favour of the culturally typical and
656 familiar four-beat metre.

657 *Learning Accuracy*

658 The ANOVA performed on the hand clapping signed asynchrony did not show a
659 significant main effect of condition, $F(1, 38) = 2.94$, $p < .094$, $\eta_p^2 = .07$. An
660 independent TOST procedure (raw equivalence bound = 0.01; based on Rose et al.,
661 2021) showed that both t tests were significant, $t_{\text{upper}}(38) = -2.17$, $p = .018$, $t_{\text{lower}}(38) =$

662 2.17, $p = .018$. Moreover, the ANOVA performed on the stepping signed asynchrony did
663 not show a significant main effect of condition, $F(1, 35) = 0.27$, $p < .606$, $\eta_p^2 = .01$. An
664 independent TOST procedure (raw equivalence bound = 0.01) showed that both t tests
665 were nonsignificant, $t_{\text{upper}}(38) = -0.74$, $p = .231$, $t_{\text{lower}}(38) = 0.74$, $p = .231$. Overall,
666 these results indicated that both the clapping and stepping accuracy during the
667 body-movement session were not significantly different between the two conditions.
668 Equivalence was established only for the clapping data, confirming that clapping
669 accuracy was *similar* across the two metre conditions.

670 **Head Movements**

671 Due to non-normality of residuals, the data were transformed using square root
672 transformation. The RM ANOVA showed no significant main effect of session, $F(1, 38)$
673 $= 1.12$, $p = .296$, $\eta_p^2 = .03$, or movement condition, $F(1, 38) = .04$, $p = .836$, $\eta_p^2 < .01$.
674 The Session \times Movement Condition interaction was also nonsignificant, $F(1, 38) =$
675 0.49 , $p = .488$, $\eta_p^2 = .01$. Overall, the results indicated that periodic head movements
676 (a) were not enhanced after vs. before the movement session and (b) were not different
677 between experimental conditions.

678 **Supplementary Analyses**

679 ***Hand Clapping***

680 To assess clapping stability during the learning session, the vector strength of
681 the asynchrony between claps and the drum cues marking the beat in each movement
682 condition was computed (Fisher, 1995; Large et al., 2015). In circular statistics, vector
683 strength values range from 0 (i.e., no synchronisation) to 1 (i.e., maximum
684 synchronisation). Following a rank-based inverse normal transformation to ensure
685 normality of residuals, the one-way independent measures ANOVA did not yield a
686 significant main effect of condition, $F(1,38) = 4.73$, $p = .036$, $\eta_p^2 = .11$.

687 ***Stepping***

688 The vector strength was also calculated for asynchronies between steps and the
689 drum cues, for all participants except two, for whom step onsets could not be extracted

690 reliably due to noisy signals. The data was then transformed using a rank-based inverse
691 normal approach to ensure normality of the residuals, and the one-way independent
692 measures ANOVA showed no main effect of condition, $F(1,36) = 1.89$, $p = .178$, $\eta_p^2 =$
693 $.05$.

694

Discussion

695 The purpose of this registered report was to provide original insights into
696 auditory rhythm perception in humans, by investigating how it is continuously shaped
697 through the interplay with motor engagement and multisensory integration.
698 Behavioural results showed a propensity to clap the metre primed in the preceding
699 body-movement session to a greater extent after vs. before the movement session,
700 showing that short-term motor engagement can shape rhythmic behaviour beyond
701 cultural experience. In contrast, EEG data did not show corresponding enhancement of
702 neural responses, suggesting that a single brief movement session may not be sufficient
703 to stabilise a metre representation that can be reactivated automatically (i.e., without
704 an explicit, related task).

705 Imprints of Motor Engagement onto Rhythm Processing

706 In line with the hypotheses, the amplitude of metre-related frequencies was
707 selectively enhanced in clapping trials performed after, relative to before, the brief body
708 movement session. This corroborates previous research demonstrating an effect of
709 priming on subsequent rhythm processing, both in infants (Flaten et al., 2022;
710 Phillips-Silver & Trainor, 2005) and adults (Chemin et al., 2014; Phillips-Silver &
711 Trainor, 2007; Su & Pöppel, 2012). The finding also extends current knowledge by
712 showing that this short-term learning effect can arise in the context of weakly periodic
713 rhythms – where there is no prominent acoustic cue to the beat periodicity in the
714 stimulus. Together, the results thus suggest that short-term motor engagement may
715 facilitate the learning of an internal representation of rhythm, or rhythm–metre
716 association, that goes beyond enhancement of already salient acoustic cues.

717 With regard to underlying mechanisms, body movements may act as a form of
718 rhythmic priming. Specifically, this priming would facilitate perceptual selection by

719 directing attention towards behaviourally relevant auditory information (Large &
720 Snyder, 2009; Large et al., 2023; Morillon et al., 2015). The resulting temporal template
721 may subsequently be recruited to guide overt movement (see Morillon & Baillet, 2017).
722 A related possibility is that metre perception is tuned through the multisensory
723 experience provided by moving the body along with external rhythmic sensory inputs,
724 yielding integration of proprioceptive, visual, auditory and tactile rhythmic inputs. Such
725 multisensory rhythms produced by body movement would thus strengthen metre
726 through self-entrainment processes (Cannon, 2025). This view is also in line with the
727 framework of embodied cognition, whereby cognitive representations dynamically
728 interact with motor systems (Witek, 2023). More specifically, movement performed
729 during entrainment to a beat is thought to inform a predictive model that in turn
730 structures perceptual processing. The richness of the multisensory experience is likely to
731 enhance the precision of this predictive model (Vuust et al., 2022). In the present study,
732 participants engaged in whole-body movement to the rhythm, specifically clapping and
733 stepping. Such movement provides robust multisensory input, which may account for
734 why even a brief movement session – relative to longer-term cultural experience – was
735 sufficient to elicit effects with a rhythm lacking prominent cues to the metre in its
736 acoustic structure.

737 **Interplay of Short-Term Motor Engagement and Longer-Term Cultural** 738 **Experience**

739 It is worth noting the cultural congruence between the stimulus and the
740 participant sample in the present study (Polak, 2026). That is, the rhythm was
741 purposely selected to match the participants' enculturation. In doing so, the study aims
742 to address a critical gap in psychology and neuroscience, by focusing on a population
743 that is still largely underrepresented in most research (see Jacoby et al., 2024;
744 Jakubowski et al., 2025; Kwon et al., 2021; Moriguchi, 2022). It also allowed to test the
745 interaction between short-term motor engagement and longer-term cultural experience
746 in rhythm processing. More specifically, repeated rhythmic patterns (often referred to as
747 ostinatos, timeline, or bell/clave patterns) are known to play a key role in providing

748 temporal reference in African(-derived) musical traditions (Agawu, 2006; Benadon,
749 2020; Polak, 2026; Poole, 2018). The use of such repeated rhythmic patterns in the
750 stimulus of the present study may therefore have elicited learned associations with
751 familiar musical repertoires, assumed to result from long-term learning process over the
752 course of enculturation, thereby activating an existing internal representation or
753 temporal template. This interpretation may account for the relative greater propensity
754 to clap according to the culturally congruent four-beat metre in the baseline session. It
755 is also corroborated by participants' debriefing statements to the question "Did the
756 rhythm remind you of something?", which explicitly associated the rhythm with cultural
757 practices (e.g., "Same rhythm as certain pieces of our traditional African music",
758 "[Rhythm of] village festivals, concerts or family celebrations", "To the beat of the
759 tam-tam in traditional African songs", "It's similar to the rhythm I often do with family
760 or friends"). This hypothesis will also be examined through cross-cultural comparisons
761 between African- and European-enculturated participants in the second Stage 2 article
762 resulting from this programmatic registered report (see Coulon et al., 2026).

763 In the current study, motor engagement affected subsequent rhythm processing
764 to a comparable degree for both three- and four-beat metre conditions – thus
765 irrespective of cultural conventions. These results suggest that African-enculturated
766 participants' meter perception is flexible (Benadon, 2020; Cameron et al., 2015; Locke,
767 2011; Temperley, 2000), especially once the temporal structure of the rhythmic pattern
768 has been grasped. These results could also be considered in relation to the relatively
769 decontextualised presentation of the stimulus used in the present study. Specifically, the
770 stimulus lacked the timbre of the instrument that typically conveys the rhythm, and
771 was isolated from other music ensemble parts and related expressive modes (e.g.,
772 dancing) in which this rhythm usually occurs.

773 Previous research has shown that Western-enculturated individuals tend to
774 organise fast musical events in groups of two or four (Bergeson & Trehub, 2006; Drake
775 & Palmer, 1993; Fraise, 1982; Møller et al., 2021; Wu et al., 2013). By contrast, the
776 present study with African-enculturated participants provided no evidence of such a

777 binary bias evident in the clapping time series. A plausible explanation is that, rather
778 than grouping the fast stream of events underlying the rhythm sequence in a binary
779 manner, African-enculturated participants relied on their cultural experience to process
780 the embedded rhythmic pattern as a whole. This holistic processing would allow the
781 rhythmic pattern to be subdivided in a binary manner, resulting in two or four
782 perceived beats per pattern repetition. Future research could disentangle these
783 possibilities by investigating how the degradation of pattern repetition across conditions
784 (for an implementation, see e.g., Coulon et al., 2025) impacts beat processing in
785 participants who are familiar with musical practices in which pattern repetition plays a
786 central role (as is the case for the cultural group tested in the present study, with the
787 so-called timelines are used as a rhythmic backbone; Agawu, 2006; Kubik, 2010; Locke,
788 1982); and by comparing these effects with those observed in European-enculturated
789 participants, as examined in previous investigation of the binary bias (Bååth, 2015;
790 Møller et al., 2021).

791 **Inconsistency Between Brain and Behavioural Responses**

792 While a brief movement session led to subsequent enhancement of metre-related
793 frequencies in the clapping responses, this was not the case for neural activity captured
794 during the post-movement listening task. In other words, the current results show that
795 a brief 20-minute movement session was not sufficient to automatically foster the neural
796 representation of learned metrical interpretations after movement cessation.

797 This may be due to the complexity of the rhythmic pattern used, which lacked
798 salient acoustic periodicities corresponding to plausible metrical interpretations (see
799 Figure 2). Such rhythms may necessitate a massive transformation of the sensory input
800 – including engagement of higher-order cortical areas – in order to be periodised into a
801 metre-related internal representation (see Lenc et al., 2021). Therefore, compared to
802 rhythms containing prominent metre-related periodicities (see e.g., Chemin et al., 2014;
803 Phillips-Silver & Trainor, 2005, 2007), rhythms with weak periodic cues may require
804 more time and repeated presentation to be robustly associated with a periodic internal
805 template.

806 Nonetheless, the current results show that, when required to move to such a
807 complex yet culturally familiar rhythm, participants were able to activate the learned
808 rhythm–metre association to guide intentional overt movements (Brower, 1993). One
809 plausible mechanism is that participants “re-enacted” the target interval duration
810 between successive movements – as in a synchronisation-continuation task – and
811 mapped this interval onto the rhythm. This strategy would allow them to maintain an
812 approximate alignment between the auditory stimuli and motor responses without
813 relying on an explicit internal representation of the metre. Such an outcome may
814 further reflect how participants approached the body-movement session. Specifically, the
815 intended process was to integrate the acoustic metre prompt with the metre as
816 embodied in the movement, and to map both onto the rhythmic pattern during motor
817 training. By contrast, participants may have instead directed their attentional resources
818 primarily on the drum sound cue in order to comply with the task and synchronise their
819 movements. This focus may have occurred at the expense of processing the broader
820 configuration of rhythm and metre as a cohesive whole (Keller & Burnham, 2005).

821 However, the interpretation that participants reproduced the target interval
822 purely from memory while ignoring the auditory input is not supported by the data. In
823 the absence of ongoing coupling between movement and sound, progressive
824 desynchronisation would be expected due to error accumulation, resulting in spectral
825 leakage and the absence of narrow peaks at the frequencies of interest. Instead, the fact
826 that clear peaks were observed in the tapping spectra points towards sustained
827 integration between the auditory input and the internal representation of metre. Hence,
828 memory for the absolute target interval alone cannot fully explain the results (although
829 it may have contributed, especially given that tempo was kept constant across sessions).

830 In any case, the cultural relevance of the rhythm, as confirmed by participants’
831 ratings on the familiarity questionnaire (see Figure 4, Panel B), did facilitate the brain
832 transformation that supports the mapping between rhythm and metre, but only when
833 the task involved active motor engagement. In this respect, it is important to emphasise
834 that the auditory stimulus used in the present study was a decontextualised version of a

835 rhythmic pattern found in African and African-derived musical traditions.
836 Consequently, contextual cues usually associated with the rhythm could not be
837 leveraged to scaffold a learned rhythm–meter association, even among participants
838 familiar with repertoires containing this pattern. This may have interfered with the
839 spontaneous activation of culturally grounded metrical frameworks, thereby limiting the
840 extent to which familiarity could exert a facilitating effect without the multimodal
841 stimulation and additional processes present during the clapping task (for discussion of
842 context effects in cross-cultural rhythm perception research, see Polak et al., 2026). In
843 addition, although participants were African-enculturated, they had all resided in
844 Belgium for an average of five years (range = 1– 15 years). These findings highlight the
845 complexity of characterising enculturation: it should not be conceived as a static
846 attribute determined solely by early exposure, but rather as a dynamic process of
847 ongoing cultural experience shaped by the context of learning and practice, and the
848 coexistence of multiple environments (Kim & Alamilla, 2017; Polak et al., 2026).
849 Accordingly, extended experience with a different cultural environment may attenuate
850 or reshape the impact of early musical experience on rhythm and metre processing.

851 **Conclusions**

852 The present findings demonstrate that even a brief engagement in body
853 movement can selectively enhance behavioural alignment with a rhythm, highlighting
854 the role of motor engagement in scaffolding internal rhythm representations, beyond
855 cultural experience. However, this enhancement does not automatically translate into
856 increased neural responses at metre-related frequencies, at least for context-free and
857 weakly periodic rhythms. The dissociation between behavioural and neural indices
858 suggests that associating internal representation of meter to complex rhythms relies on
859 multi-level processing, and that such association is not achieved through a single, brief
860 movement session. Taken together, these findings provide empirical support for the
861 interactive contributions of motor engagement, multisensory integration, and cultural
862 experience in shaping rhythm perception. The obtained results thus offer novel insights

863 into the mechanisms by which the brain flexibly maps rhythmic inputs onto holistic
864 internal templates.

865 **Open Practices**

866 ***Data Availability***

867 Pilot data, along with all anonymised raw and processed data supporting the
868 reported analyses, are available on a public Zenodo repository
869 (<https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10221480>).

870 ***Code Availability***

871 The scripts used to conduct the power analysis and all scripts supporting the
872 reported analyses are available on a public GitHub repository
873 (https://github.com/segoleneguerin/meter_learning_motor).

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882 Writing – review & editing. E. C.: Conceptualisation; Methodology; Formal analysis;
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888 **Competing Interests**

889 The authors have no competing financial interests to declare.

890

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Table 1*Estimated Required Sample and Effect Sizes*

Question	Hypothesis	Analysis plan	Sampling plan	Rationale for deciding the sensitivity of the test for confirming or disconfirming the hypothesis	Interpretation given to different outcomes
The amplitude of neural responses at metre-related frequencies will be enhanced after vs. before the movement session, and this effect will be magnified in the four-beat metre condition.	\bar{z}_{EEG} will be larger after when compared to before movement (H_{1a}). \bar{z}_{EEG} post movement will be larger for the four-beat metre condition when compared to the three-beat metre condition (H_{1b}).	Pairwise t test Mixed-model ANOVA (Movement Condition \times Session) followed by pairwise t test	$N = 8$ ($d = 1.53$; $\alpha = .020$; $1-\beta = .90$) $N = 20$ for the interaction effect ($f = 0.89$; $\alpha = .020$; $1-\beta = .90$) and $N = 6$ for the simple effect ($d = 1.77$; $\alpha = .020$; $1-\beta = .90$)	Small telescopes approach ($d_{\text{SESOI}} = 0.47$). Small telescopes approach ($d_{\text{SESOI}} = 0.47$).	The hypotheses will be accepted if the statistical test is significant ($p < .020$) and the associated Cohen's $d > d_{\text{SESOI}}$.

(Continued)

<p>Movement will enhance the amplitude of metre frequencies in the clapping signal, and the four-beat metre condition will yield the most powerful effect.</p>	<p>$\bar{z}_{\text{clapping}}$ will be larger after when compared to before the movement (H_{2a}).</p>	<p>Pairwise t test</p>	<p>$N = 6$ ($d = 1.77$; $\alpha = .020$; $1-\beta = .90$)</p>	<p>Small telescopes approach ($d_{\text{SESOI}} = 0.47$).</p>	<p>The hypothesis will be accepted if the statistical test is significant ($p < .020$) and the associated Cohen's $d > d_{\text{SESOI}}$.</p>
	<p>$\bar{z}_{\text{clapping}}$ post movement will be larger for the four-beat metre condition when compared to the three-beat metre condition (H_{2b}).</p>	<p>Mixed-model ANOVA (Movement Condition \times Session) followed by pairwise t test</p>	<p>$N = 20$ for the interaction effect ($f = 0.89$; $\alpha = .02$; $1-\beta = .90$) and $N = 6$ for the simple effect ($d = 1.77$; $\alpha = .020$; $1-\beta = .90$)</p>	<p>Small telescopes approach ($d_{\text{SESOI}} = 0.47$).</p>	

Note. Statistical power, planned analyses, and critical statistical tests for each research hypothesis. H = Hypothesis; RM ANOVA = Repeated-measures analysis of variance; SESOI = smallest effect size of interest.

Figure 1

Experimental Design and Material

Note. Panel A: Diagrammatic representation of the experimental design. Panel B: Rhythmic pattern with the overlaid drum sound that was used during the body-movement session in the three-beat (left) and four-beat (right) metre condition. Icon sources: ‘EEG’ by Aenne Briemann, ‘Clap hand’ by Ainul Muttaqin, and ‘Dancing’ by Jack (modified) from the Noun Project under CC BY 3.0 license.

Figure 2*Auditory Stimulus Analyses*

Note. Panel A: Spectrum of the acoustic stimuli. The grey bars represent the first and last frequency of the spectrum that were discarded (see “Sound Analysis” subsection). Panel B: Normalised spectrum amplitudes. Panel C: Averaged z scores. Each dot represents an individual frequency and the horizontal line represents the mean value. Three-beat metre related frequencies (i.e., 1.25 and 3.75 Hz) are highlighted in orange and four-beat metre related frequencies (i.e., and 0.83, 1.67, 3.33, and 4.17 Hz) in blue. a.u. = arbitrary unit.

Figure 3

Data-Processing Pipeline

Note. ICA = independent component analysis; FFT = fast-Fourier transform; freq. = frequency; ANOVA = analysis of variance. Icon sources: ‘Music and multimedia’ by Colourcreatype (modified), ‘Dancing’ by Jack (modified), ‘Clap hand’ by Ainul Muttaqin, ‘Head’ by Hunotika (modified), and ‘EEG’ by Aenne Briemann (modified) from the Noun Project under CC BY 3.0 license.

Figure 4

Demographic Data and Familiarity with the Rhythmic Pattern

Note. Panel A: Demographic information (gender, age and country of origin). For the country of origin, the home country of the participant was used only when themselves have lived in this country for the first 15 years of their lives; otherwise, the home country of the participant's parents was used. DRC = Democratic Republic of Congo. Panel B: Ease, likeability, and familiarity with the rhythmic pattern. Data were collected at the end of the experimental session the using a 5-point Likert scale (see Supplementary File 1).

Figure 5

Neural Responses during the Pre- and Post-Movement Session

Note. Panel A: Time domain EEG signals averaged across participants and chunked over one pattern duration, shown for both sessions and conditions. EEG signals are overlaid on the stimulus envelope (in grey). Panel B: Magnitude spectra of neural responses averaged across participants separately for each session and condition. Three-beat and four-beat related frequencies are highlighted in red and blue, respectively, and metre-unrelated frequencies are shown in black. Time- and frequency-domain responses were merged across conditions in the pre-movement session, as experimental conditions only differed in the subsequent body-movement session. Panel C: Normalised z scores (i.e., range of -1 to +1) at metre-related frequencies across sessions and conditions. Individual values are shown as scatter points, with medians and quartiles represented by boxplots.

Figure 6

Behavioural Responses during the Pre- and Post-Movement Session

Note. Panel A: Inter-response intervals (IRIs) of hand-clapping responses for all participants before and after the body-movement session. Medians and quartiles are indicated by dots and vertical lines, respectively. In the pre-movement session, most participants clapped close to plausible metre periodicities (coloured horizontal lines), whereas responses in the post-movement session shifted towards the beat periodicities learned in each condition. Participants were sorted by their median IRI for each session separately. Panel B: Magnitude spectra of clapping responses averaged across participants for both sessions and conditions. Three-beat and four-beat metre-related frequencies are highlighted in red and blue, respectively, and meter-unrelated frequencies are highlighted in black. Note that IRIs and the magnitude spectra from all participants were merged across conditions in the pre-movement session as experimental conditions only differed in the body-movement session. Panel C: Normalised z scores (i.e., range of -1 to +1) at metre-related frequencies across sessions and conditions. Individual values are shown as scatter points, with medians and quartiles represented by boxplots. *** $p < .001$.